

Pioneering new migration routes: central Asian truck drivers' experiences in the EU

Giulio Benedetti, Arnis Sauka, Milena Pavlova, Olga Zvonareva & Wim Groot

To cite this article: Giulio Benedetti, Arnis Sauka, Milena Pavlova, Olga Zvonareva & Wim Groot (10 Apr 2025): Pioneering new migration routes: central Asian truck drivers' experiences in the EU, Central Asian Survey, DOI: [10.1080/02634937.2025.2479099](https://doi.org/10.1080/02634937.2025.2479099)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02634937.2025.2479099>

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group

[View supplementary material](#)

Published online: 10 Apr 2025.

[Submit your article to this journal](#)

Article views: 959

[View related articles](#)

[View Crossmark data](#)

Pioneering new migration routes: central Asian truck drivers' experiences in the EU

Giulio Benedetti ^{e,f}

^aMaastricht Graduate School of Governance, Maastricht University, Maastricht, The Netherlands;

^bDepartment of Business and Management, Stockholm School of Economics in Riga, Riga, Latvia;

^cDepartment of Health Services Research, CAPHRI, Maastricht University Medical Center, Maastricht University, Maastricht, The Netherlands; ^dDepartment of Health, Ethics and Society, CAPHRI, Maastricht University, Maastricht, The Netherlands; ^eMaastricht Graduate School of Governance, Maastricht University, Maastricht; ^fDepartment of Health Services Research, CAPHRI, Maastricht University, Maastricht, The Netherlands

ABSTRACT

A new stream of migration from Central Asia to countries of the European Union is being spearheaded by workers employed in the truck driving industry. This is part of a trend of increasing diversification of the destinations of migration from Central Asia. This paper examines how drivers exert their agency when choosing between migration destinations. To do so, we interviewed twenty Kyrgyz and Uzbek drivers about the differences they perceived between working in Europe and their previous experiences in Russia. We find that new work migration flows to the EU are following an established pattern in which costs associated with labour are sustained in the destination country, and the costs of social reproduction are borne in the origin country. Results also suggest that when presented with multiple destination options, migrant workers can strategize within the boundaries imposed by the overall terms of migration.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 23 May 2024

Accepted 23 February 2025

KEYWORDS

Migration; labour; migration infrastructures; Kyrgyzstan; Uzbekistan; European Union

Introduction

In recent years, an increasing number of migrant workers from post-Soviet Central Asia have moved to countries of the European Union. Between 2020 and 2022 alone, the number of citizens of the five Central Asian countries who received a residence permit from EU member states went from 76,388 to 153,792, a doubling in two years. Most of these migrants held Kazakh, Uzbek or Kyrgyz passports, and their countries of destination were primarily Germany, Poland and Lithuania (Eurostat 2023).

The increase in migration from post-Soviet Central Asian countries toward EU member states has happened in the context of the increasing diversification of migration flows

CONTACT Giulio Benedetti giulio.benedetti@sseriga.edu

 Supplemental data for this article can be accessed online at <https://doi.org/10.1080/02634937.2025.2479099>

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The terms on which this article has been published allow the posting of the Accepted Manuscript in a repository by the author(s) or with their consent.

originating from Central Asia. While most Central Asian migrants are still employed in Russia, in numbers estimated to be between five to eight million individuals (Eraliev and Urinboyev 2020; Schenk 2023), alternative destinations are becoming increasingly popular, including Turkey (Akcapar and Çakır 2024; Urinboyev and Eraliev 2022), South Korea and Japan (Dadabaev and Soipov 2022) and the USA (Tsoy, Dinh, and Djurabaeva 2023). The context in which this diversification is taking place is that of the combination of increased economic and political unpredictability in Russia, together with active governmental policies in countries like Uzbekistan aimed at fostering this diversification (Erdoğan 2021). For migrants, this means that there is a growing number of people who were previously working in Russia and now consider moving to different destinations.

Between 2020 and 2023, more than half of new residence permits issued to citizens of Central Asian countries for employment purposes were provided by Poland and Lithuania (Eurostat 2024, see the Appendix in the online supplemental data). The two countries are major hubs of the hauling industry in the EU, which has suffered severe labour shortages in the last few years (IRU 2022), partly addressed by the stark increase of recruitment of drivers from extra-EU countries (Baranska and Picard 2023). Some of the vacancies in the sector are being filled by Central Asian citizens, which is particularly clear in the example of Lithuania: in 2022, the majority of newly registered migrants were of Central Asian origin (59%), and most of the work permits (78%) have been issued to workers employed in the logistic sector (Linava 2023). In Poland, the number of truck driver licenses issued to Central Asian citizens totals to roughly half of the new work permits issued to workers from the same region (Eurostat 2024; GITD 2023). The sudden increase in migration to the EU suggests that we are looking at a new stream of migration in its early phases. Studies have shown that migrant workers often initially leave their country with the intention of spending only a limited time abroad, but they may end up changing their plans afterward, often for family reasons, such as the prospect of a better education for their children (Gurieva, Kõiv, and Tararukhina 2020; Von Loeffelholz 2016).

Experiences of migration to Russia, which still is by far the largest destination country for Central Asian workers, have been documented at length. Scholars have looked at how migrants access healthcare (Amirkhanian et al. 2011), housing (Demintseva 2017) and jobs (Heusala and Aitamurto 2017), but also at how experiences of migration are shaped by economic and social factors (Agadjanian, Gorina, and Menjívar 2014; Gabdulhakov 2019; Turaeva and Urinboyev 2021; Vorobeveva 2023), and by formal rules and their interpretation (Reeves 2013, 2015; Schenk 2021; Turaeva 2023). These studies go into depth in describing the experiences of migrants in Russia and have resulted in increased interest in and have broadened the scope of the analysis. Recent studies have sought to interpret experiences of migration in the broader distribution of resources across the post-Soviet region (Kangas et al. 2023), and as shaping geopolitical narratives (Eraliev and Urinboyev 2023). Some studies have also sought to explore the differences in experiences across different ethnic groups (Agadjanian, Menjívar, and Zotova 2017; Gerber and Zavisca 2020), uncovering the hierarchical nature of the racial categorization of migrants in Russia. To our knowledge, however, there have been no studies yet on the experiences of Central Asian migrants who have been to multiple destinations.

Prospective migrants to Europe are faced with regulatory conditions that differ from the ones they have met in Russia. The European migration regime requires workers to obtain a formal invitation, upon which a visa will be issued. Typically, workers get in contact with an enterprise in Europe and visit a local consulate to obtain a visa once the hiring firm has provided an invitation. In contrast, workers who migrate from Central Asia to Russia are required to obtain documents only after they reach their destination, and regulatory regimes vary depending on the origin country of the worker. Citizens of countries that are members of the Eurasian Economic Union (EEU), including Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, are subjected to a facilitated regime, and exempted from obtaining a specific ‘patent’, a work permit to which all other migrants from Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) countries are subjected. In both cases, the regulatory regime is also a source of precarity for migrant workers: in Russia, this is due to the arbitrariness of law enforcement and bureaucratic loopholes (Schenk 2021), while research has shown that in Europe it is also the strength of the rule of law can contribute to migrants’ precarity (Eraliev 2023).

The new stream of migration to Europe is also made possible by technological factors. Information about hauling jobs in Europe is available on the Internet, and interviews with candidates are conducted over the phone, after filling out a questionnaire. Here the situation in Europe differs in that Central Asian migrants are usually more proficient in the Russian language, which has a relatively limited number of speakers within the European Union. Institutional and technological dimensions shape the ‘human’ side of migration infrastructures. Social networks of migration are widespread in both contexts, but understandably more pronounced in Russia, where the number of migrants from Central Asia is substantially higher and migration began already during Soviet times, although in much lower numbers than what happened in the post-independence period (Abashin 2014). The institutional dimension also conditions the role of intermediaries of migration: given the visa regime in Europe, middlemen can be expected to be found in the origin countries, while in the case of Russia, they are likely to be more present in the destination country.

In this paper, we describe and analyse the experiences of Central Asian truck drivers who had worked in Russia and decided to migrate to the European Union afterward. While Russia has been for many years the main and almost only destination for Central Asian migrants, the opening of a new route puts prospective migrants in front of a choice. By looking at how truck drivers compare their experiences in the EU with earlier ones they had in Russia, we look at the reasons behind the choice of embarking on a new route. In doing so, we obtain more insight into the role of infrastructures in shaping migrants’ choices and to broaden our understanding of how destinations of Central Asian migration are increasingly diversified.

Background

By the beginning of the twenty-first century, scholarship on migrations gradually moved away from a focus on individual mobilities to the factors that shape and condition migration. The attention to factors that push and pull individual agents who aim to maximize their returns (see Harris and Todaro 1970; Todaro 1969) has given way to an increased interest in collective mobilities and the social networks in which they take

place (Massey 1990). The scholarly conversation has then pivoted toward the factors that shape and constrain mobilities, setting the institutional and regulatory boundaries within which networks operate (Hannam, Sheller, and Urry 2006). Following this general direction, recent scholarship has suggested the unit of analysis to be the infrastructures of migration, composed of distinct but overlapping domains of operation that cut across regulatory, commercial and social dimensions (Xiang and Lindquist 2014).

Looking at migration through the prism of infrastructures allows researchers to consider migrants who move together with the actors and contextual factors that move them, and to focus on mobility together with the conditions that allow and shape mobility (Lin et al. 2017). Migration infrastructures are ‘the systematically interlinked technologies, institutions and actors that facilitate and condition mobility’ Xiang and Lindquist (2014, 124). They can be articulated into five dimensions, interlinked and overlapping each other. Two refer to institutional and technological conditions, while three concern the ‘human side’ of migration, and they comprise migrant social networks, intermediaries of migration and the humanitarian side, which refers to non-governmental organizations.

More recently, a logistical ‘gaze’ of migrations has been proposed as a complementing analytical figure that considers the principles behind the infrastructures of labour migration (Krifors 2021). The agencies and brokers that are key agents of infrastructures increasingly operate in a logic that can be traced in the processes of contemporary logistics. Migrant workers are mobilized ‘just in time’ and ‘to the point’, in the spirit of a ‘delivery’ rationality (Altenried et al. 2018). In this sense, value is added through the coordination of transnational social disparities with the costs of displacement, and cultural differences are mobilized to this end (Rossiter 2016). Through this process, migrant workers are recruited from the same locality and conveyed to cover a specific job segment in the destination country.

To achieve integration of supply networks, intermediaries actively undertake a quest for interoperability across different markets, in an effort to gain a sufficient level of standardization of work and migration practices between different groups of workers and destinations (Krifors 2021). Studies on the logistics and infrastructures of migration have so far devoted more attention to the costs associated with labour, in that focusing on the structural aspect of contemporary migrations has enabled a very productive look at the role of intermediaries of migration. Moreover, this approach has provided the instruments to look at the relationship between the intermediation of migration and the productive processes and the central role that employers have in migration (McKeown 2012).

Adopting a logistical point of view allows us to unpack the calculations made by different actors on the routes of contemporary labour migrations. The viability of the operations of economic actors such as agencies and intermediaries depend on the coordination of costs associated with the labour of migrants. Their role is to provide workers who have the right skills, at the right moment, at a competitive cost, to the industries that need them. This analytic approach allows us to look at what makes migration possible. It explains the mechanisms of labour migration but leaves less space for the reasons that lead migrants to set off on their path. While a focus on infrastructures and logistics of migrations doesn’t necessarily entail neglecting migrants’ agency (Chua et al. 2018 Lin et al. 2017);, so far this aspect has been overshadowed by the predominant focus on structural aspects and the agency of intermediaries.

From the workers' perspective, the sustainability of migration is not only linked to the salary offered, but also to the costs that they will have to bear and the time they will have to spend to continue to be able to live and work. To bring back migrants' choices and their rationale, we propose to complement the focus on labour costs advanced by the logistical approach with a focus on the broader costs that migrants encounter to sustain such labour. Prospective migrant workers need to weigh the offered salary over the costs and time associated with the social reproduction of labour, or 'the processes that enable the worker to arrive at the door of their place of work every day' (Bhattacharya 2017, 1). Social reproduction theory (SRT) looks at labour and time as interconnected elements that sustain capitalism through both productive and reproductive spheres. Productive labour, or wage work, is complemented by reproductive labour, which includes caregiving and household tasks that regenerate labour power daily (Bhattacharya 2017). While the reproductive sphere remains largely unpaid, it represents costs that need to be waged by prospective migrants.

Workers employed on a regular contract, such in the case of the truck drivers who are the protagonists of this study, also need to perform practices of social reproduction, both in their day-to-day activities and in their long-term planning, and those are central elements for the calculations of pros and cons of a migration perspective. Migrant workers need to consider not only the salary they will be offered but also the availability of accommodation and health-care, which will allow them to return to work shift after shift. They will also have to consider long-term questions relative to their families and their perspectives on retirement.

This paper focuses on migrant agency in the context of a new migration route is that bringing truck drivers from Central Asia to the European Union. By looking at how drivers compare their experiences in the EU and Russia, we focus on the reasons that brought them to choose the new route over the old one. Rather than limiting our inquiry to the relative level of salaries and prices, we consider the drivers' perception of time, and how they look at the activities connected to the social reproduction of labour. By doing so, we aim to complement the literature on infrastructures and logistics of migration by looking at the activities that sustain the social reproduction of labour, which are at the core of the calculations made by migrant drivers. We look at how the migration process appears in the migrants' calculations, and at how migrants exercise agency by strategizing between different migration routes.

Methodology

Migrant drivers spend long periods of time in their trucks. Although European regulations would mandate drivers to have periods of rest at regular intervals (Eurlax 2020), it is not uncommon for drivers to spend up to six months living and sleeping in their trucks, in what amounts to a policy adopted by many firms to cut costs (Gardingen and Atema 2023). Because of this, telecommunication devices play an important role in the lives of drivers, as they often use their smartphone and internet connection to keep in contact with their colleagues and families.

Life behind the wheel makes drivers become immersed in a system of online communication that revolves around WhatsApp chats and Telegram channels. There, drivers exchange information and news. These can range from the discovery of new halal shops across Europe to advice on the best internet provider in different countries, and

from advice on migratory issues to commenting on videos on YouTube or TikTok released by the many drivers-influencers. Truck drivers are greatly familiar with holding conversations over the phone, and through voice messages or video calls: their degree of familiarity with this medium is so high that having a conversation with them in person or through the phone usually makes very little difference, and it is not uncommon that they call each other spontaneously while on the road.

Migrant drivers are formally registered in an EU member State, but they spend most of their time in places of transit across the whole continent. While their bodies dwell on roads, parking lots and their trucks, their social life takes place largely online, and through telecommunication devices. To grasp this diversity, we organized the recruitment of participants in two phases: the first in person, and the second through the social media environment that absorbs so much of the time and attention of the drivers.

Drivers from Uzbekistan were invited to take part in the study in person, in a parking lot near Frankfurt-am-Main (Germany). This was the site of the first strike in Europe that involved only migrant truck drivers from post-Soviet countries, and it saw the participation of roughly 60 Georgian drivers and 11 Uzbek. The strike took place from March to April 2023, and the principal researcher joined the workers on the strike for a week, sharing common spaces and daily activities with the drivers until the action was coronated with success and the drivers dispersed again.

Access to the site of the strike was facilitated by union officials and activists supporting the workers, in the measure in which a friendly welcome on their part reassured the workers on strike of the legitimate intentions of the researcher. However, research activities proceeded independently by activists' oversight, and the proper introduction to the workers was made by the principal researcher himself, who was able to communicate in Russian, a language that most of the workers spoke.

The group of Uzbek drivers on strike was presented with the aims of the research and protection of their personal data through informal conversations, in which it was also ascertained that the migration trajectories of the potential participants shared a degree of similarity, without clear outliers. The group was then invited to self-select some participants, who happened to be the ones who were more willing to engage in a longer conversation and those who felt they had more command of the Russian language. They also appear to have been those more often volunteering to liaise with the larger group of Georgian strikers and with the union officials. While the Uzbekistani group had no clear leaders, the volunteers were also the ones more often engaged in speaking up for their comrades during assemblies.

During the second phase, which took place in the following months, we focused on recruiting Kyrgyz participants through truck drivers' chat groups and conducting interviews with them over the phone. In this effort, we were assisted by a Kyrgyz native speaker, who took on the same role as union officials in reassuring them of the legitimate nature of the inquiry, but also supported us in introducing potential participants to the aim of the study, standards of protection of personal data, and to the identity of the researchers involved. He also conducted a preliminary informal screening of participants, aimed at recruiting truck drivers specifically already working in Europe. While in this case, the use of Kyrgyz language was useful in fostering trust and overcoming the potential obstacle posed by an online acquaintance, we chose to hold interviews in Russian as knowledge of this tongue is widespread among Central Asian migrants. Three decades

after the collapse of the Soviet Union, the Russian language is still part of everyday life in Central Asia, especially among those with life experience in Russia. For these reasons, we considered that adopting Russian as the language of our conversations would have been appropriate.

During both phases, we ensured the conditions of confidentiality and voluntary participation, as no remuneration was offered. We kept conducting interviews until we reached saturation of data, or in other words until no new elements started appearing during interviews. The study was introduced to migrant drivers as a way to make their voices heard, and to document their stories of migration for scientific knowledge. We started our conversations by asking questions about the context of migration: how the participant had travelled to Europe and which difficulties did he encounter. Then we moved on to asking about their previous work and life experiences in Russia, and in what they differed from those they met in the European Union. Finally, we asked about the reasons for their choice and about their future plans, which offered an additional way to interpret the experiences they just elaborated on.

We approached the data by adopting the method of reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke 2006, 2019). In doing so we looked at data in distinct but interconnected phases, which allowed us to combine relative flexibility with the rigour of thematic analysis (Saldaña 2014). We conducted the analysis in the following stages (Byrne 2022):

- (1) Familiarization with the data through manual transcription.
- (2) Generation of initial codes relative to interactions of migrants with intermediaries.
- (3) Generation of themes, by aggregating and systematizing existing codes.
- (4) Revision of potential themes in light of their pertinence, boundaries, thickness, meaningfulness and internal coherence.
- (5) Definition and naming of themes.
- (6) Production of the final report.

Results

We conducted a total of 20 in-depth interviews, lasting around one hour each. Most respondents are Kyrgyz ($n = 16$), while four are from Uzbekistan. Table 1 presents a description of the participants' characteristics: they are rather evenly distributed in terms of age, which range from 26 to 53. More than half of them ($n = 11$) grew up in an urban setting, and the other half ($n = 8$) are from the countryside. Most of them are registered for work in Lithuania ($n = 11$), followed by Poland ($n = 7$) and Slovakia ($n = 2$). All but two reported being married and having children in their home countries, and the majority of them ($n = 15$) said they had work experience in Russia. Those who didn't work in Russia showed nevertheless a great degree of acquaintance with the situation in the country, which relied on accounts heard by close family members or friends. Only a few of the respondents had previous work experience as truck drivers, while a number of them had acquaintance with similar jobs, such as taxi driving or working at a vehicle repairing facility. Many however were at their first experience, having worked in different fields, ranging from shopkeeping to being part of the army.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics.

Participant	Age (years)	Country	Region of origin	Country of employment
1	26	Kyrgyzstan	Osh	Slovakia
2	29	Kyrgyzstan	Osh	Lithuania
3	26	Uzbekistan	Fergana	Poland
4	41	Uzbekistan	Tashkent	Poland
5	47	Uzbekistan	Tashkent	Poland
6	50	Uzbekistan	Tashkent	Poland
7	37	Kyrgyzstan	Bishkek	Lithuania
8	35	Kyrgyzstan	Bishkek	Lithuania
9	28	Kyrgyzstan	Talas	Lithuania
10	28	Kyrgyzstan	Bishkek	Poland
11	41	Kyrgyzstan	Issyk-kul	Lithuania
12	36	Kyrgyzstan	undisclosed	Lithuania
13	37	Kyrgyzstan	Talas	Lithuania
14	28	Kyrgyzstan	Bishkek	Lithuania
15	53	Kyrgyzstan	Bishkek	Lithuania
16	45	Kyrgyzstan	Bishkek	Slovakia
17	53	Kyrgyzstan	Issyk-kul	Lithuania
18	37	Kyrgyzstan	Bishkek	Poland
19	29	Kyrgyzstan	Bishkek	Lithuania
20	38	Kyrgyzstan	Jalal-Abad	Poland

Migration infrastructures

‘Friends just said: “Come [to Russia], work, you’re welcome, nothing to worry about.”
(Respondent 4, Uzbek, 41-year-old)

The feeling of pioneering a new migration route is recurrent among the drivers we interviewed. Asked about the differences between the new and the old destinations, they painted two quite distinct pictures. Migrating to Russia is associated with the presence of many relatives, friends and acquaintances who already know the country and work there. Jobs are often found upon arrival through word of mouth or with the help of others. The language is familiar, and so are the rules of the game, so to speak: how to deal with employers, with authorities and with local people. Conversely, accounts of migrating to Europe usually start by telling about the search for a job before departing, and the collection of the necessary documents. There are fewer people they know with knowledge about working in Europe, and the languages spoken there are foreign, and they act as a barrier when trying to understand legal technicalities and practices.

This difference creates an economic cost of migration to Europe. Prospective migrants need to secure an employment offer and then a visa before flying to their destination. A worker willing to secure documents by himself would need to organize a trip to Almaty (Kazakhstan) where Eastern European consulates are located, pay consular fees, and then dwell in the city until their documents are processed, before finally leaving by plane. This process costs several hundreds of euros, equivalent at least to two months of local salary, but it can cost up to two thousand euros when agencies or informal intermediaries are involved in the process. Respondents indicated that usually people borrow money from friends or banks to finance migration, or they may sell their car or land plot. In general, however, respondents didn’t report major problems in obtaining documents for working in Europe, which is likely connected to the various policies that are put into place to ease the chronic job demand of the European hauling sector (IRU 2022).

The choice of recurring to agencies and intermediaries is not obligatory, but it is preferred, especially by those undergoing their first experience or by older people, who may feel less acquaintance with the internet. After the first or the second period spent in Europe however, most drivers usually feel they know the procedure well enough to do it by themselves. Registered agencies and informal intermediaries may offer to make the job search for their clients or to submit their documents to consular authorities. Respondents also reported that a few companies, once contacted, refer to some informal ‘helpers’ who arrange documents and organize the travel for a fee. However, usually, the role of intermediaries ends when drivers reach Europe, meaning that intermediaries usually don’t have any control over drivers’ lives in Europe, nor can they help if problems arise.

‘I came here and it is difficult with the language. Well, you don’t know the language, neither with whom to speak.’ (Respondent 11, Kyrgyz, 41-year-old)

In contrast, respondents indicated that in Russia they didn’t have to worry about documents until they reached the country, making this destination cheaper. The presence of many fellow countrymen also contributed to reducing costs and uncertainty, as there are more people to potentially ask for help. At the same time, issues with documents and being asked for bribes by police officials were also recurrent, in line with what has been observed by previous research (Schenk 2021). In some cases, people were also scammed in their workplace and paid less than promised, albeit the issue of being cheated (‘obmanyvali menya’) seems to be lived with rage but accepted as a widespread feature of migration.

The majority of respondents reported that they received help from friends and acquaintances in finding a job, which came free of charge. While at first look it could be possible to limit the categorization of intermediaries to the agencies and brokers who enable migration to Europe, it should also be noted that while the help received in Russia was often not remunerated in monetary terms, it was surely in the form of gratitude and trust, as shown by the way respondents spoke about their acquaintances. Despite the higher costs of migrating to Europe, travelling to Russia also didn’t come for free. In both cases, respondents indicated that they had to borrow money or sell their car or plot of land to finance their migratory endeavours.

Perceptions about the different migration procedures to Russia and the EU are mixed, and connected to one’s own experience. Kyrgyz workers, whose country is part of the Russia-led Eurasian Economic Union and are subjected to a simplified migration procedure, tended to say that migrating to Russia was easier, while Uzbek workers were more prone to say that procedures to EU countries were simpler, or very similar to Russian ones, in that obtaining a work patent on Russian soil, or a work visa in a European consulate were rather similar processes.

Work relations

‘You know, in Russia there are many jobs, but they don’t pay well.’ (Respondent 10, Kyrgyz, 28-year-old)

Respondents mentioned higher salaries as the primary reason for them choosing Europe over Russia. This decision reflects not just a static comparison but also concerns about the

growing uncertainty surrounding the value of the ruble. This is in line with the findings of recent studies about the diversification of migration destinations for Central Asian workers (see Eraliev and Urinboyev 2023). Economically, new opportunities in the EU have emerged as a result of international tensions, which have made EU wages relatively more appealing and stable compared to investing time and effort in employment within Russia. While most respondents spoke of economic motivations, two drivers also mentioned holding a dual Kyrgyz-Russian citizenship: wanting to avoid conscription, they said they found themselves unable to keep travelling to Russia.

However, migration decisions are not only borne out of aspirations, such as those induced by the prospect of higher salaries, but are also based on practical possibilities (De Haas 2021). The drivers pictured a contrast between the large availability of different jobs in Russia, against truck driving being almost the sole option in the EU. While some respondents were offered a few alternative job opportunities by migration agencies, usually in manufacturing or construction, economic conditions didn't make these offers appealing. As we will see in more detail in the following sections, respondents described Russia as a place where a multitude of contacts could be mobilized for obtaining a job, while options regarding Europe were limited to fewer acquaintances and agencies. This highlights on the one hand how a new migration infrastructure is emerging, and on the other, a recurring pattern in EU migration where workers from specific regions are directed into particular employment sectors on the continent (Altenried et al. 2018).

Respondents' recollections about work conditions in Russia are mixed. Some said they had a satisfactory time in the country: job characteristics and accommodation were as promised, and management showed a good attitude toward migrant workers. Drivers sharing these memories are usually those who have work experience in the mining industry or provincial towns, like those located in the Far East. While work is described as physically demanding, positive feelings are associated with getting what is expected and agreed upon. Honest, hard work that can be done for a few months in exchange for an acceptable salary. In contrast, drivers who travelled to major cities such as Moscow or Saint Petersburg often reported worse experiences. Employed usually as taxi drivers or construction workers, they recalled long shifts, being employed often in the informal sector, and being in contact with the diverse humanity of the great cities, not always for the good. While higher costs reduced their margin of earning, migration was inscribed in a narrative that sets that time apart as temporary, and as a moment separated by life itself: it is a time in which the only goal is to work and earn money. In this sense, ignoring the flow of life seemed easier in the isolated workplaces of the Far East rather than in Moscow and Saint Petersburg. This element of outright separation between the time and place of work from that of life, as we will see, is also recurrent in accounts of work in the EU.

Most of the drivers who arrive in Europe, as they explain, have no prior experience in the hauling industry, making the salaries offered by European companies particularly attractive. Job postings often advertise daily wages of €60 to €80, a significant contrast to the average monthly salaries in Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan, which are approximately \$400 and \$300, respectively (StatKg 2024; Uzstat 2024). Work contracts are usually temporary and they are provided with a Russian translation. Although the companies can terminate contracts very quickly, the high demand for drivers and the fact that many

companies are hiring on a rolling basis provide a sense of security about the possibility of securing employment. When new drivers arrive, they are usually trained by companies for about a week and then they are sent on a 'stage' period for no less than a month, in which they will accompany another driver, taking turns behind the wheel when needed. During this period they will also be provided with the necessary documents such as the Code 95, the certificate that allows them to drive on European roads, and a residence permit.

In Europe, drivers spend most of their days alone, scattered along parking lots on highways and at the points of loading and delivery. European regulations compel drivers to observe mandatory period of rest while driving, and set at 13 h the maximum length of a work shift. However, due to a flexible interpretation of how to account for waiting times, it is not uncommon for drivers to be available for work for up to 15 h in a day. As reported by respondents, they also usually sleep in their trucks: few companies provide guesthouses for drivers to rest during mandatory breaks, such as weekends, so many haulers end up spending months sleeping in their truck cabins. While this contravenes EU regulations (Eurllex 2020), it often amounts to a cost-saving policy for many companies. Respondents also reported issues with the payment of salaries: while work contracts are often presented to them with a Russian translation, they are usually ill-equipped to educate themselves in the technicalities of national and EU regulations. In some firms, this leads to partial withholding of salaries or the arbitrary imposition of fines (see Gardingen and Atema 2023).

On the site where Uzbek respondents were recruited, the main reason for them to go on strike was in fact that the Polish company for which they were working was making every effort to avoid paying them what it had promised. Those efforts included exorbitant fees for accommodation for the first week of training, systematic underreporting of worked hours, and arbitrary fines for imagined infractions. In one case, for example, a driver told us he was fined for having had his fuel stolen while sleeping. In that case, the company argued that as the driver had chosen to pay for accommodation in a hostel instead of guarding his truck during the weekend, he was to pay 750€ for damages, which would be subtracted from his next salary. When the drivers decided to stop the trucks and strike, a conservative estimate of what they had been withheld reached 97,585€.

While salary issues are widespread but usually more frequent in some companies rather than others, lack of healthcare is a more systemic issue. Asked about the security of the job, one of our respondents described the situation in the following way.

'Well, it's a dangerous work. There was an accident I know about, two people are gone already, dead. They were my acquaintances, we met, we ate together. It's a dangerous job, I wouldn't recommend it to everyone. [...] Another guy was hit with a knife by some people. He was at the gas station, and when he left the cabin they hit him with a knife. Thank God all went well, he got to the hospital. There was also one guy whose cabin caught fire, he was inside and a fire broke out. He jumped off the cabin but his face got burned nevertheless. [...] I don't know about insurance, generally, they send you home if you have serious injuries, but I don't know whether the company helped, and nobody spoke about money. Usually, when something bad happens, we Kyrgyz who work here collect money to send people back, so they have money for the trip. It means the guy got no money [from the company].' (Respondent 10, Kyrgyz, 28-year-old)

This segment introduces a recurrent theme, by which all serious healthcare matters are meant to be dealt with at home, which is a complication, especially for older drivers,

who bring up the issue more frequently. For all of them however, this is only another element of a clear geographical division of their time: all issues related to work pertain to the time spent in Europe, and all issues and hopes related to life are left for their home country.

Despite all the difficulties of a precarious and dangerous job, respondents describe truck driving across Europe as rewarding, primarily in economic terms. Seeing these workers as victims would contrast the way they see themselves. Respondents didn't say work conditions in Europe are worse than in Russia, and on the contrary, several of them said that working in the EU is generally better. This aligns with a generally positive way to present their current situation, suggesting that they see themselves as more successful than those who decided to emigrate to Russia, but also more successful than those who didn't leave the country: they are potentially up for earning way more than what they would have at home, and there is pride in this.

Expectations

'Well, you go to the metro, you sit at your place there. If there is next to you a Russian man, fancily dressed: you see it, a Muscovite. Well, he stands up and he changes his seat. He's not going to stay next to you, and he gazes at you with such eyes, like you're some kind of third-class person.' (Respondent 15, Kyrgyz, 53-year-old).

Respondents described their expectations by depicting the new destination in rather brighter terms than the old one. In general, they consistently associated Russia with racism, experienced through contacts with people or public officials. There are some differences, however, which often overlap with work satisfaction. Those who went working in isolated places such as mining, construction sites or factories in the Far East or far north, usually recollected fewer instances of racism, while those were very present and vivid in the memories of those who travelled to the bigger cities, such as Saint Petersburg and especially Moscow, indicated by many as the worst place in terms of racist attitudes. Smaller cities in the countryside were also mentioned by those who had experience as truck drivers in Russia as places where they would encounter racism. In general, respondents tended not to talk about major incidents that occurred to them but rather about a climate of hostility and micro-aggressions. In this sense, they didn't say they felt in danger, but rather 'chuzhie', foreign: uneasy and unwanted.

On the contrary, respondents often indicated that they expected Europe to be more welcoming, mixing an ideal of better social relations with the image of the EU as more sensible to upholding the rule of law and civil rights. This combination, that brought several respondents to use the term 'more civilized' about the EU, was also thought to be in opposition to the idea of Russia as 'more corrupt', both in terms of the awkwardness of attitudes toward foreigners and in terms of the arbitrariness of law enforcement.

'People are gentler than in Russia. Here they answer normally, they explain things to you. With respect.' (Respondent 20, Kyrgyz, 38-year-old)

The EU is expected by many to be more rigorous in upholding the rule of law and civil rights. Some differences also apply to this vision. While it is beyond the scope of this study to give a full analysis of the events surrounding the strike of drivers where some

of the interviews were collected, it can be noted that those responses shared a great degree of appreciation for the solidarity of Europeans and Germans in particular. Respondents on the site of the strike experienced, on one part, the very negative attitude of their Polish employer but, on the other, were often surprised to have found the dedicated help of German trade unions, and the solidarity of the inhabitants of the region where they held their strike. They recounted the awe they felt when people from nearby villages brought them food and shelter, and how they offered to wash their clothes for free. This had a great impact on how respondents felt Europe to be inhabited by friendly and welcoming people.

At the same time, there is also a difference in the perception of different countries, which becomes gradually more evident among those drivers who arrived first and have now spent more time in the EU, and who are usually starting to have a less idealized vision of Europe. Sensing that European countries are also not at all immune to intolerance, they noted that in the Eastern European environments in which they interacted episodes of racism happened more often than in Western Europe. While they mentioned countries as the unit of their recollections, it has to be noted that respondents mostly spoke about their interactions, which take place typically in three specific environments: the firms they work for, where they interact with managers and accountants; the companies where they load or unload their cargoes, where they come across workers and site managers; and parking lots along the highways, where they get in touch with colleagues.

Within these boundaries, the answers of several respondents coincided in indicating experiences in France or Spain to be the best ones, recollecting being invited for coffee by welcoming operators in locations of truck loading and downloading, while Italy, where encounters were reported to be more mixed and sometimes marred with racist episodes, was yet also renown for the patience of locals in helping drivers at finding their way around narrow roads, the most hated sorrow of drivers in a country that otherwise reminded some of them of the climate of their home countries. Germany and the Netherlands were appreciated for the punctuality of their loading and downloading operations. In contrast, respondents often noted a more discriminatory attitude in Eastern Europe, of which the most common examples were to be given orders rather than requests, sometimes being shouted at without reason, and especially experiencing precedence being given to white drivers when waiting in queue to load or download for delivery.

One element of presenting the EU as a preferable destination over Russia is also related to environmental considerations. One recurrent topic of negative recollections toward the time spent in Russia is connected to its rigid winters, and how the long cold season and the lack of sun makes it an inhospitable country for those who are used to the climate of Central Asia. In contrast, the EU is also seen as a new land to discover, one which is also famous for tourist attractions. Several drivers reported how their job, which brings them to travel at length through Europe, also allows them to do some sightseeing. While dwelling constantly in their trucks is demanding, it also means that they often find themselves spending their free time in new localities. As the quasi totality of them has never been to Europe before, they often get the opportunity to do some tourism. There are several social media accounts, run by truck drivers, dedicated to showing their sightseeing activities in Europe.

Discussion

Central Asian truck drivers are leading the way in the opening of a new migration route, and their experience offers insight into how infrastructures of migration are formed. Results show a considerable degree of internal coherence of their answers and they point to a number of differences as well as similarities encountered by migrants in the two destinations. Among the differences, they indicated their expectations, the procedures of migration, and to some degree also work conditions.

The drivers spoke of work conditions in the EU as heavy, challenging and dangerous, but overall more remunerative and better than working in Russia, stressing their satisfaction with their current choice of destination. Employment is precarious by default in both destinations and seen as temporary by nature, something subject to continuous strategy when conditions may change. While the old Russian destination is perceived as cheaper, easier and a place where many acquaintances and fellow countrymen can help find a job and solve problems, the European destination presents some novelty. Procedures of migration are another area in which the two destinations are experienced in a different way. In contrast to Russia, where jobs are found after arrival, migrating to Europe requires finding a job and the necessary documents beforehand, which entails higher costs and the participation of registered agencies and informal intermediaries who may help with documents and the search for a job.

There are also high expectations, which influence the drivers' migration strategy. While Russia is consistently associated with racism, newcomers from Central Asia expect countries of the European Union to be more welcoming. If they spoke of Russia as a corrupted country, many expressed with confidence that the EU would be more attentive to the rule of law and human rights. However, they also highlighted differences between different locations in both areas. In Russia, accounts of racism were more frequent among those who had work experiences in the major cities rather than among those who worked in remote areas such as mining sites and factories in the Far East, where they arguably had less contact with the wider population. In the EU, respondents consistently spoke of experiences with people in the Western part of the Union to be more satisfactory than in the Eastern countries, where the companies they work for are located.

One crucial element, however, is constant across both destinations: the way drivers looked at time. Respondents referred to migration as a period of intense work, separated by life 'proper', whose features – healthcare, family, building a house – are consistently reserved for their home country. The widely shared objective is to earn enough money to return home and build a house for one's own family. In this sense, expectations about precarious employment in Russia are replicated in Europe and the same stark distinction between the time spent working that related to all matters of social reproduction is redeployed for migration to Europe.

There is continuity in a mode of migration in which there is a clear separation between costs related to the work activities, which pertain to life in the destination country, and costs regarding social reproduction, which are borne in the home country (Kangas et al. 2023). This division of labour, in which resources earned through work in Russia are reinvested into communities in Central Asia, can be also traced in the importance of migration remittances for Central Asian countries, especially Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan,

but also Uzbekistan (Abashin 2013). Remittances earned in Russia influence social practices in the origin countries such as weddings, which are often both the goal of saving accumulation during the first years of migration (Gerber and Zavisca 2020) and social practices through which the accumulated wealth is reinvested in local economies and in strengthening relations of trust (Cleuziou 2019).

In the case of truck drivers, the geographical separation between private life and labour is functional to the search for interoperability of the labour supply by hiring companies, and the coordination of social disparities, displacement costs and cultural differences to the end of reducing the cost of labour (Krifors 2021). The clear separation between the time of production and social reproduction allows companies to relegate all costs related to social security, healthcare and long-term accommodation to the origin country of migrant workers. They, in turn, are in the position to accept these conditions because the salary they earn will buy better services and better housing in their country, where prices are lower. In this sense, the costs of migration are organized by companies following a logistic rationale, and migrant workers accept precarious and dangerous work conditions with the hope of minimizing costs for themselves by playing along in the same logic of functional separation of the times of production and social reproduction.

The experience of truck drivers is an exemplary case in which the global shift toward the adoption of a logistics rationale in labour migrations is brought to the extreme. Truck driving is a job on the move by definition, as workers are usually separated from the places and time of their social reproduction for longer periods than other categories of workers. The case of Central Asian truck drivers shows how the characteristics of the job are pushed to the limits for migrant workers, exposing the contradictions of this way of labour organization. While according to the law, they would have to return home periodically, their time of production is often compressed into one long shift, and workers live in their trucks for months. Just as the separation between the productive and reproductive times of life is pushed to the extreme, so is the coordination of costs in a multi-national, de-territorialized logic. Drivers are formally registered to be working in Eastern Europe and earn their salaries there, but they are physically on the move, and usually in Western Europe. When drivers receive their pay checks, they evaluate them with their mind in yet another space, with different prices, which is their origin country.

The case presented in this study concerns the very recent opening of a new migration route, and it may offer some suggestions for future research. First, the respondents we asked to elaborate on their experiences in Russia are all people who find themselves in Europe. Thus, their answers explain the background of their migration choices, and they don't have a comparative value about migrants' conditions in the two countries. Such a research direction, which would need to involve also participants based in Russia, may provide valuable insight into the labour processes in the two neighbouring areas. Secondly, this study focuses on a new infrastructure of migration at a precise stage, while it is being developed. However, research has shown that infrastructures of migration change over time, and their evolution may entail substantial changes (Xiang and Lindquist 2014). Further research will be necessary to assess how relations between drivers and intermediaries of migration will evolve as the infrastructure connecting Central Asia to Europe becomes more established. Thirdly, the hauling industry presents conditions that are peculiar to this sector, such as relatively higher wages than other professions available to Central Asian migrants

in Europe. The sector also presents a strategic importance for the functioning of the whole economy (Chua et al. 2018). The picture presented in this study of a migration stream that is mostly formalized shouldn't be generalized beyond the boundaries of this specific sector. Comparing this case with migrant labour in other sectors of the economy, which may often be more informal and less remunerated, may also provide important insights into the geographies of migrant labour from Central Asia.

Conclusion

We asked 20 truck drivers from Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan to compare their experiences of work migration in the European Union and Russia. We interpreted the results by looking at how respondents motivated their choice to embark on the newly open migration path to Europe's haulage industry instead of choosing the old Russian destination. The drivers described several differences between the two destinations. Russia is described as a cheaper destination, where many fellow countrymen may offer help in case of need; migrating to Europe requires securing documents in advance, which makes it costlier but it is more rewarding in terms of salary. Work conditions are also described as partially different, and more formalized in Europe's hauling sector. However, respondents also noted that work was hard and precarious in both destinations. Especially, the perception of time was similar in both locations: work time is perceived as something separated from life itself, in that all work activities are reserved for the country of destination, and all activities of social reproduction such as healthcare, long-term housing and family are enacted in the country of origin, where price levels are lower. The similarity in how these activities are kept – even geographically – separated suggests that the experiences of this particular group of migrants are informed by a logistic organization of labour migration, that reduces costs by separating the time of work by social reproduction expenditures. While this is a recurrent feature of experiences of migration, in the case of truck drivers the separation between 'life' and 'work' is brought to the extreme. Results also suggest that the opening of multiple destinations allows migrant workers to strategize and exercise their agency within the boundaries set by overarching logistical ways of organization of migration. Migrant workers evaluated differences between the two destinations but were also aware of the possibility of deploying similar strategies in both contexts and adapting the knowledge acquired during pre-existing experiences to a new destination, which they went on to pioneer.

Acknowledgements

We would like to extend our heartfelt thanks to Mr Ruslanbek Malabekov, who assisted in the collection of interviews and was of great help to the realization of this study. We would also like to express our gratitude to the participants, without whom this study wouldn't have been possible, and we hold the hope of having contributed to making their voices heard. We would also like to thank the activists and union officials in Grafenhausen, for the kind support offered during the days of the strike, and the two anonymous reviewers, for the helpful comments on the early drafts of this study.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

Research for this article was supported by funding from the European Commission through a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network grant under the Horizon 2020 Programme (project 'Markets', grant agreement No. 861034).

Ethics

Ethical clearance was granted by the Ethics committee at Stockholm School of Economics in Riga on 8 September 2023. In accordance with the standards indicated in the ethics statement, anonymized data is available upon request to the corresponding author.

ORCID

Giulio Benedetti <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-6563-5224>

Arnis Sauka <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-7708-4375>

Milena Pavlova <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-6082-8446>

Olga Zvonareva <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-5548-7491>

Wim Groot <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-1035-5916>

References

- Abashin, S. 2013. "Central Asian Migration." *Russian Politics & Law* 51 (3): 6–20. <https://doi.org/10.2753/RUP1061-1940510301>.
- Abashin, S. 2014. "Migration from Central Asia to Russia in the New Model of World Order." *Russian Politics & Law* 52 (6): 8–23. <https://doi.org/10.2753/RUP1061-1940520601>.
- Agadjanian, V., E. Gorina, and C. Menjivar. 2014. "Economic Incorporation, Civil Inclusion, and Social Ties: Plans to Return Home among Central Asian Migrant Women in Moscow, Russia." *International Migration Review* 48 (3): 577–603. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imre.12117>.
- Agadjanian, V., C. Menjivar, and N. Zotova. 2017. "Legality, Racialization, and Immigrants' Experience of Ethnoracial Harassment in Russia." *Social Problems* 64 (4): 558–576. <https://doi.org/10.1093/socpro/spw042>.
- Akcapar, S. K., and D. Çakir. 2024. "Feminization of Labour Migration from Uzbekistan to Turkey: The Role of Neoliberal Policies, Patriarchy and Social Networks." *Central Asian Survey*.
- Altenried, M., M. Bojadžijev, L. Höfler, S. Mezzadra, and M. Wallis. 2018. "Logistical Borderscapes: Politics and Mediation of Mobile Labor in Germany After the 'Summer of Migration'." *South Atlantic Quarterly* 117 (2): 291–312. <https://doi.org/10.1215/00382876-4374845>.
- Amirkhanian, Y. A., A. V. Kuznetsova, J. A. Kelly, W. J. DiFranco, V. B. Musatov, N. A. Avsukevich, N. A. Chaika, and T. L. McAuliffe. 2011. "Male Labor Migrants in Russia: HIV Risk Behavior Levels, Contextual Factors, and Prevention Needs." *Journal of Immigrant and Minority Health* 13 (5): 919–928. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10903-010-9376-y>.
- Baranska, P., and S. Picard. 2023. *Third-Country Drivers in European Road Transport*. European Transport Workers' Federation.
- Bhattacharya, T. 2017. *Social Reproduction Theory: Remapping Class, Recentring Oppression*. For Work / Against Work. London: Pluto Press.
- Braun, V., and V. Clarke. 2006. "Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology." *Qualitative Research in Psychology* 3 (2): 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp0630a>.
- Braun, V., and V. Clarke. 2019. "Reflecting on Reflexive Thematic Analysis." *Qualitative Research in Sport, Exercise and Health* 11 (4): 589–597. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2159676X.2019.1628806>.
- Byrne, D. 2022. "A Worked Example of Braun and Clarke's Approach to Reflexive Thematic Analysis." *Quality & Quantity* 56 (3): 1391–1412. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-021-01182-y>.

- Chua, C., M. Danyluk, D. Cowen, and L. Khalili. 2018. "Introduction: Turbulent Circulation: Building a Critical Engagement with Logistics." *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space* 36 (4): 617–629. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263775818783101>.
- Cleuziou, J. 2019. "Traditionalization, or the Making of a Reputation: Women, Weddings and Expenditure in Tajikistan." *Central Asian Survey* 38 (3): 346–362. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02634937.2019.1617247>.
- Dadabaev, T., and J. Soipov. 2022. "Revisiting Labor and Educational Migration from Uzbekistan to Japan and South Korea." In *The Grass is Always Greener?*, edited by T. Dadabaev, 11–46. Singapore: Springer.
- De Haas, H. 2021. "A Theory of Migration: The Aspirations-Capabilities Framework." *Comparative Migration Studies* 9 (1): 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40878-020-00210-4>.
- Demintseva, E. 2017. "Labour Migrants in Post-Soviet Moscow: Patterns of Settlement*." *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies* 43 (15): 2556–2572. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2017.1294053>.
- Eraliev, S. 2023. "The Shadow Side of Migration: Exploring the Nexus Between Undocumentedness, Informality and Crime among Uzbek Migrants in Sweden." *Nordic Journal of Criminology* 24 (2): 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.18261/njc.24.2.5>.
- Eraliev, S., and R. Urinboyev. 2020. "Precarious Times for Central Asian Migrants in Russia." *Current History* 119 (819): 258–263. <https://doi.org/10.1525/curh.2020.119.819.258>.
- Eraliev, S., and R. Urinboyev. 2023. "What Have You Done, Brother Putin?: Everyday Geopolitics and Central Asian Labour Migration to Russia." *Central Asian Survey* 0 (0): 1–20.
- Erdoğan, Z. 2021. "Uzbekistan's Transformation with the New Uzbek Strategy: Shifting Policies Towards Mediation of Labor Migration Through Migration Infrastructure." *MANAS Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi* 10 (Özel Sayı): 157–171. <https://doi.org/10.33206/mjss.992826>.
- Eurlex. 2020. Regulation (EU) 2020/1054 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 July 2020. Accessed March 2024. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2020/1054/oj>.
- Eurostat. 2023. All Valid Permits By Age, Sex and Citizenship on 31 December of Each Year. Accessed November 2023. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/MIGR_RESVAS__custom_7218139/default/table.
- Eurostat. 2024. First Permits Issued for Remunerated Activities by Reason, Length of Validity and Citizenship. Accessed November 2024. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_resocc__custom_13806451/default/table?lang=en. https://doi.org/10.2908/migr_resocc.
- Gabdulhakov, R. 2019. "In the Bullseye of Vigilantes: Mediated Vulnerabilities of Kyrgyz Labour Migrants in Russia." *Media and Communication* 7 (2): 230–241. <https://doi.org/10.17645/mac.v7i2.1927>.
- Gardingen, I., and E. Atema. 2023. "Widespread Exploitation in the EU Road Transport Industry: The Case of Central Asian Truck Drivers." Road Transport Due diligence foundation.
- Gerber, T. P., and J. Zavisca. 2020. "Experiences in Russia of Kyrgyz and Ukrainian Labor Migrants: Ethnic Hierarchies, Geopolitical Remittances, and the Relevance of Migration Theory." *Post-Soviet Affairs* 36 (1): 61–82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1060586X.2019.1680040>.
- GITD. 2023. Main Inspectorate of Road Transport. Cited in: Pakulniewicz, M. (2024) The Dark Side of Recruiting Drivers from Far Afield. More and More Cases are Coming to Light. Accessed February 2025. <https://trans.info/en/recruiting-drivers-from-abroad-385446>.
- Gurieva, S., K. Kõiv, and O. Tatarukhina. 2020. "Migration and Adaptation as Indicators of Social Mobility Migrants." *Behavioral Sciences* 10 (1): 30. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs10010030>.
- Hannam, K., M. Sheller, and J. Urry. 2006. "Editorial: Mobilities, Immobilities and Moorings." *Mobilities* 1 (1): 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17450100500489189>.
- Harris, J. R., and M. P. Todaro. 1970. "Migration, Unemployment and Development: A Two-Sector Analysis." *The American Economic Review* 60 (1): 126–142.
- Heusala, A.-L., and K. Aitamurto, eds. 2017. *Migrant Workers in Russia: Global Challenges of the Shadow Economy in Societal Transformation*. New York: Taylor & Francis.
- International Road Transport Union. 2022. Driver Shortage Global Report 2022. IRU Intelligence Briefings. Accessed March 2024. www.iru.org.

- Kangas, A., D. Krivosos, S. Khidjobova, Z. Omonillaeva, O. Jitlina, A. Tereshkina, and M. Kiromova. 2023. "Social Reproduction of Post-Soviet Migrant Labour: Braiding the International Political Economy." *Antipode* 55 (1): 156–179. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anti.12871>.
- Krifors, K. 2021. "Logistics of Migrant Labour: Rethinking How Workers 'Fit' Transnational Economies." *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies* 47 (1): 148–165. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2020.1754179>.
- Lietuvos nacionalinė vežėjų automobilių asociacija "Linava". 2023. Most Work Permits for Foreigners in 2022 Issued in the Transport Sector. January 30, 2023. Accessed November 2024. <https://www.linava.lt/naujienos/daugiausiai-leidimu-dirbti-uzsienieciams-2022-m-isduota-transporto-sektoriuje/>.
- Lin, W., J. Lindquist, B. Xiang, and B. S. A. Yeoh. 2017. "Migration Infrastructures and the Production of Migrant Mobilities." *Mobilities* 12 (2): 167–174. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17450101.2017.1292770>.
- Massey, D. S. 1990. "The Social and Economic Origins of Immigration." *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 510 (1): 60–72. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716290510001005>.
- McKeown, A. 2012. "How the Box Became Black: Brokers and the Creation of the Free Migrant." *Pacific Affairs* 85 (1): 21–45. <https://doi.org/10.5509/201285121>.
- Reeves, M. 2013. "Clean Fake: Authenticating Documents and Persons in Migrant Moscow." *American Ethnologist* 40 (3): 508–524. <https://doi.org/10.1111/amet.12036>.
- Reeves, M. 2015. "Living from the Nerves: Deportability, Indeterminacy, and the 'Feel of Law' in Migrant Moscow." *Social Analysis* 59 (4): 119–136. <https://doi.org/10.3167/sa.2015.590408>.
- Rossiter, N. 2016. *Software, Infrastructure, Labor: A Media Theory of Logistical Nightmares*. New York: Routledge.
- Saldaña, J. 2014. "Coding and Analysis Strategies." In *The Oxford Handbook of Qualitative Research*, edited by P. Leavy, 581–605. Oxford University Press.
- Schenk, C. 2021. "Producing State Capacity Through Corruption: The Case of Immigration Control in Russia." *Post-Soviet Affairs* 37 (4): 303–317. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1060586X.2021.1955325>.
- Schenk, C. 2023. *Post-Soviet Labor Migrants in Russia Face New Questions Amid War in Ukraine*. Migration Policy Institute. Accessed August 2023. <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/article/labor-migrants-russia-ukraine-war>.
- StatKg. 2024. National Statistical Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic. Stat.kg. Accessed November 2024.
- Todaro, M. P. 1969. "A Model of Labor Migration and Urban Unemployment in Less Developed Countries." *The American Economic Review* 59 (1): 138–148.
- Tsoy, A., K. T. Dinh, and S. Djurabaeva. 2023. "Understanding Migration and Resettlement Experiences of Uzbek Immigrants in the United States." *Graduate Student Journal of Psychology* 20: 153–176. <https://doi.org/10.52214/gsjp.v20i1.10308>.
- Turaeva, R. 2023. "Capitalising Precarity: Wellbeing of Migrants in Russia." *Journal of Labor and Society* 1 (aop): 1–18.
- Turaeva, R., and R. Urinboyev, eds. 2021. *Labour, Mobility and Informal Practices in Russia, Central Asia and Eastern Europe: Power, Institutions and Mobile Actors in Transnational Space*. New York: Taylor & Francis.
- Urinboyev, R., and S. Eraliev. 2022. *The Political Economy of Non-Western Migration Regimes: Central Asian Migrant Workers in Russia and Turkey*, 192. Cham: Springer Nature.
- Uzstat. 2024. Statistics Agency Under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Stat.uz. Accessed November 2024.
- Von Loeffelholz, H. D. 2016. "Managing Highly-Skilled Labor Migration in Germany: Law and Practice." In *Labor Migration and Migrant Integration Policy in Germany and Russia*, edited by M. S. Rozanova, 59–75. Saint Petersburg State University.
- Vorobeva, E. 2023. "Overcoming the Mobility Bias in Transnational Entrepreneurship." *Global Networks* 23 (4): 884–900. <https://doi.org/10.1111/glob.12424>.
- Xiang, B., and J. Lindquist. 2014. "Migration Infrastructure." *International Migration Review* 48 (1_suppl): 122–148. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imre.12141>.